

inoculum is prepared by soaking 10 g rice seed hulls in 30 ml normal saline solution for 2 h, then concentrating the solution to 10% of its original volume by centrifuging at 4,000 g for 20 min.

The percentage of varieties showing positive reaction by IRMA varied with origin (see table). The lowest was

47.4% and the highest 100% (all seeds were from a diseased area). In general, the majority of the seeds from diseased areas were more or less infected. The CI method was less sensitive than IRMA.

Similar results were obtained for disease-free seed samples by both

IRMA and CI methods. For diseased seed samples detected by IRMA, however, only 67% showed a positive reaction to the CI test. IRMA is a more effective and reliable seed inspection method. □

Physiochemical treatments to break dormancy in rice

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We studied the effects of three physiochemical treatments on breaking dormancy in rice, using 200 healthy seeds of IR36, IR34, and H4 per treatment. Two weeks after harvest in 1988, seeds were kept at 50 °C dry heat for 5 d, soaked 20 h in 0.1 N HNO₃ solution, or dehulled. Seeds germinated in petri dishes were counted 5 d after.

Germination varied among varieties and treatments (see table). IR34 could be considered a strongly dormant

Rice seed germination with different dormancy-breaking treatments. China, 1988.

Variety	Germination (%)				Mean ^a
	No treatment	50 °C dry heat	HNO ₃ soaking	Dehulled	
IR36	81	92	87	46	76.5 a
IR34	37	75	52	26	47.5 b
H4	84	97	88	86	88.0 a
Mean ^a	67.3 bc	88.0 a	75.7 ab	52.7 c	70.7

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by *t*-test

variety—only 37% of its untreated seeds germinated. With 50 °C dry heat treatment, 75% germinated; with soaking in HNO₃, 52% germinated. Germination in weakly dormant IR36 and H4 also was stimulated by the two methods. The dry heat method was significantly better than the no treatment.

Hull removal did not produce any better results than no treatment, perhaps because the dormancy factor (or germination inhibitor) may be in the seed coat rather than in the hull, or it could be due to mechanical injury to seeds during dehulling. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management – inorganic sources

Response of rice to pyrite topdressing at different fertilizer levels

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Pyrite contains 22-24% total sulfur, 20-22% Fe, 0.5-0.8% MgO, 0.1% CaO, 0.6-0.8% alumina, 35-40% silica, 2-3% C, 0.02% Zn, 0.05% Cu, and 0.01% Mn. We noticed farmers using pyrite on their rice crops. This led us to test six pyrite rates and one Zn application at three fertilizer levels. The treatments in a split-plot design with three replications are given in the table.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.5, EC (1:2) 0.09 dS/m, 0.42% organic C, 17.5 kg available P/ha, 135 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract), CEC 8.8

meq/100 g soil, 180 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), and 0.86 ppm available Zn (DTPA extractable).

Grain yield of rice with different fertilizer levels and pyrite topdressing at Masodha, Faisabad, India, 1985.

Fertilizer combination (NPK kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							Mean
	No pyrite	0.2 t/ha	0.4 t/ha	0.6 t/ha	0.8 t/ha	1.0 t/ha	5% ZnSO ₄ spray	
Low (60:13:25)	4.0	4.2	4.3	4.5	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3
Medium (80:18:33)	4.1	4.4	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.8	4.6	4.6
High (120:26:50)	4.4	4.8	5.0	5.0	5.1	5.3	5.1	5.0
Mean	4.2	4.4	4.6	4.7	4.7	4.8	4.7	
LSD (P =0.05)		Fertility 0.40		Pyrites 0.20				
CV (%)		4.66						

All the P and K and half the N were applied as basal before transplanting. Rice cultivar Sarjoo 52 was transplanted 18 Jul 1985. Pyrite was topdressed but not incorporated 20 d after transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed at tillering and panicle

initiation.

Each fertilizer level increased grain yield significantly. Increasing pyrite levels showed a linear yield response at all fertilizer levels except the low level. There was no interaction between pyrite rate and fertilizer rate.

Several aspects of pyrite application-application time, long-term application on normal soils, and causes of yield increases-are being studied. □

Effect of source and level of phosphorus on rice - grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*)

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We evaluated the effect of P level on yield of rainfed lowland rice - grass pea cropping sequence in 1988-89. P sources were single superphosphate, ammonium polyphosphate liquid 16:32% NP, and IFFCO-complex. The 5.0- × 2.5-m plots were laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was clayey loam with 0.60% organic C, 0.06% total N, 17 kg available P and 187 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8. IR36 was transplanted 17

Jul, 22 d after seeding, at 25- × 25-cm spacing, with four seedlings/hill. Fertilizer was broadcast at transplanting. N and K in P sources were calculated and urea and potassium chloride used to total 50-25 NK/ha.

One day before rice harvest on 30 Oct, grass pea cultivar Nirmal seeds (25 kg/ha) were broadcast uniformly over the rice crop. Immediately after rice harvest, half the plot was covered with 1.0 t/ha rice straw mulch. Grass pea was harvested 27 Feb 1989.

Rice grain yield did not differ with P source (see table). Grass pea grain yield was best with residual P from single superphosphate.

Rice straw mulch on grass pea after rainfed lowland rice was superior to no-mulch for both grass pea grain and straw yields. □

Effect of source and level of P on grain and straw yields of rice and grass pea. Kalyani, West Bengal, India, 1988-89.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Rice		Grass pea	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
<i>Source of P</i>				
Single super-phosphate	4.5	4.6	2.2	2.5
Ammonium poly-phosphate	3.8	3.8	2.0	2.0
IFFCO-complex	4.1	4.3	1.8	2.0
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.7	0.1	0.2
<i>Level of P (kg/ha)</i>				
4.4	3.5	3.7	1.8	1.9
8.8	4.3	4.8	2.1	2.2
13.2	4.6	4.1	2.1	2.3
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.7	0.1	0.2
<i>Rice straw mulch (t/ha)</i>				
0.0	-	-	1.4	1.3
1.0	-	-	2.6	3.0
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.1	0.1

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Nitrogen equivalence of green manure for wetland rice on coarse-textured soils

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We studied the relative effect of green manure N and inorganic N on rice grain yield in field experiments in 1986-88. Soil was loamy sand to sandy loam with pH 7.4 to 8.2, 0.30-0.40% organic C, and 0.06-0.08% total N.

Green manure crops *Sesbania aculeata*, sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea*, and cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* were sown the first week of May and incorporated at 50 to 60 d old 1 d before transplanting rice. Total biomass and N in the green manure crops were determined at incorporation.

In plots without green manure, four levels of urea (0 to 180 kg N/ha) were applied in equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting. Basal 13-25 kg PK/ha was applied at transplanting.

Rice grain yield with urea alone increased significantly up to 180 kg N/ha. The grain yield data were fitted to quadratic response functions and the fertilizer N equivalence of green manure N computed (the amount of

inorganic N required to produce yields similar to those obtained with green manure alone).

Green manure added 41-150 kg N/ha depending on the source. In general, green manure N was equal to or better than urea N in increasing grain yield of rice (see table). The N equivalence was 35% higher than urea N and for cowpea, 20% for sunn hemp, and 15% for sesbania. □

Inorganic N equivalence of green manure in wetland rice. Ludhiana, India, 1986-88.

Green manure	Experiments (no.)	Green manure N added (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		Inorganic N equivalence (kg/ha)
			No green manure	Green manure	
Sesbania	5	45- 75	3.3	5.0	72
	11	97-150	3.6	6.3	136
Sunn hemp	3	41- 70	3.1	4.5	72
	2	101-140	3.5	7.1	148
Cowpea	4	55 - 80	3.1	5.5	98